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The creativity of composer Halyna Ovcharenko in the Ukrainian-European Dialogue of Cultures

To date, there are many gaps in the study of Ukrainian musical culture in a holistic compendium of all its components, including the work of representatives of both mainland Ukraine and the Ukrainian diaspora. Researching the works of Ukrainian composers who lived and worked in different regions of Ukraine, as well as those who emigrated to other countries for various reasons, opens up new pages of cultural interactions, enriches our understanding of the contribution of artists who identified themselves with Ukraine to the treasury of European and world musical culture. We can state the discovery and involvement of many little-known and undeservedly forgotten names of prominent composers of the Ukrainian diaspora in the music and concert practice of recent decades, including Fedir Yakymenko (France), Marian Cousin (France), Stefania Turkevych-Lukiyanyovych (UK), Antin Rudnytsky (USA), Roman Prydatkevych (USA), Yuri Fiala (Canada), and many others.

Ukrainian composer Halyna Ovcharenko (*1963) belongs to the community of artists who are currently successfully representing Ukraine in Europe. She has significant creative achievements that have been repeatedly recognized both in Ukraine and abroad. However, the work of this talented composer has not yet become the subject of musicological research, which is why the proposed article is relevant.

A lot of research is devoted to Halyna Ovcharenko's work in national and regional periodicals (newspapers *Kultura i Zhyttia*, *Pravda Ukrainy*, *Vechirni Kyiv*, *Khreshchatyk*, magazines *Muzyka*, *Folk Art and Ethnography*, English-language edition *News from Ukraine*, etc.). Their authors are Iryna Drach,¹ Halyna Stepanchenko,² Inna Klyshko,³ Lesia Lantsuta,⁴ Hanna Prykhodko,⁵ Alla Tereshchenko,⁶ Yurii Chekan,⁷ Nina Shurova,⁸

¹ Drach, Iryna: "While the cuckoo crows...", *Music*, 1996, № 2; Drach Iryna. „Revival of the spiritual tradition“, *Ukrainian musical culture: searches, achievements, prospects*, Sumy, 1996.

² Stepanchenko, Halyna: „Tragic chords of the Requiem“, *Folk art and ethnography*, 1993, № 5–6, pp. 38–40.

³ Klyshko, Inna: „The Call of the Past...“, *Chervonyi Promin'*, 1997, January 17.

⁴ Lantsuta, Lesia: „Women's portraits in the interior“, *Chas/Time*, 1995, October 27.

⁵ Prykhodko, Hanna: „The unfading Mallow“, *Posvit*, 1995, № 4.

⁶ Tereshchenko, Alla: „Woman who has a thousand names“, *Pravda Ukrainy*, 1995. November 17.

⁷ Chekan, Yurii: „At the festival map“, *Kultura I Zhyttia*. 1992, October 17; Chekan Yurii: „Two poles of Halyna Ovcharenko's artistic world“, *Chas/Time*, 1996, January 26; Chekan, Yurii. „Contours of the festival“, *Muzykal'naya Akademiya*, 1993, № 1, pp. 58–59; Chekan, Yurii: „Tragic chords of the festival“, *Vechirni Kyiv*. 1992. October 23; Chekan, Yurii: „Immortalization in music“, *Khreshchatyk*, 1992, October 15.

⁸ Shurova, Nina: “First Steps”, *News from Ukraine*, 1992, № 12.

Nataliia Yarosh.⁹ Among the foreign publications that have repeatedly paid attention to Ovcharenko's works is the British magazine *The Independent*.¹⁰ Ovcharenko's work is covered on the pages of the electronic *Encyclopedia of Modern Ukraine*¹¹ as well as the prestigious *The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians*.¹²

A successful start. Formation of Halyna Ovcharenko's personality and the beginning of her creative activity in Ukraine

Halyna Ovcharenko (Galina Ovčarenko, Галина Овчаренко) was born on July 9, 1963, in the small mining town of Novodruzhesk (Новодружеськ), Sievierodonetsk district (Севєродонецький район), Luhansk region (Луганська область). Her remarkable musical abilities led her to one of the most prestigious educational institutions in Ukraine for musically gifted youth, the Mykola Lysenko Kyiv Secondary Specialized Music School, where she studied from the age of 12. The next stage in the formation of Ovcharenko's musical professionalism was her studies at the Kyiv State Conservatory, composition class of Professor Yurii Ishchenko, which she successfully completed in 1987. Ovcharenko's first compositional successes date back to the 1980s, when she was a student. Almost all of her compositions were performed at national and international music festivals. These were piano, chamber, choral works, and music for children: six pieces for voice and piano *Children's Pictures* (1980), *Three Choruses* for mixed a cappella choir (1981), *Sonata* for piano (1985), *Quintet* for string quartet and clarinet (1986), *Cantata* for children's choir, symphony orchestra, and soloists (1987), and three pieces for choir *Vesnuvannia (Springing)*, 1989).

Halyna Ovcharenko's works of the first half of the 1990s revealed the young composer's versatile creative personality and the vivid national identity of her musical language. A great creative success was the work for choir, soloists, reciter, and symphony orchestra *Burnt Mallow* based on the poem by Valentyna Otroshchenko (1992). It was a deeply personal H. Ovcharenko's creative reflection on the Chernobyl tragedy, which was embodied in a large-scale vocal and symphonic composition. The work was performed by the Symphony Orchestra of the National Television and Radio Company of Ukraine under the direction of Volodymyr Sirenko at the International Festival "Kyiv Music Fest" in 1992. Also in the first half of the 1990s, the composer's oeuvre included such works as Five Pieces for Symphony Orchestra *Dribushechky* (1992), *Toccata* for Trumpet (1993), *Two Pieces for Inspired Clarinetist* for clarinet solo (1995), and other

⁹ Yarosh, Nataliia. "A golden cloud spent the night...". *Vash shans*, 2000, September 27.

¹⁰ Signes of perfection in minimal movement. *The Independent on Sunday*, 2000, May 21. <http://www.halynaovcharenko.com/index.php>.

¹¹ Shurova, Nina: „Ovcharenko, Halyna Ivanivna“, *Encyklopediia Suchasnoii Ukrainy*. https://esu.com.ua/search_articles.php?id=74792.

¹² Shurova, Nina: „Ovcharenko, Halyna“, *The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians*, New York, 2001, vol. 18, p. 817.

works. Close creative cooperation brought Ovcharenko together with musicians from Canada – the famous piano duo Lyuba and Irenei Zhuk. At their request, she wrote the *Concerto for Two Pianos Hopak* (1992) and the work for two pianos *Wizard World in Pieces of Ice* (1994).

Ovcharenko's active scientific and pedagogical work in the leading art educational institutions of Ukraine began in the mid-1980s, when she was a student. In 1986–1993, she taught at her Alma Mater, the Mykola Lysenko Kyiv Secondary Specialized Music Boarding School (now the Mykola Lysenko Kyiv State Music Lyceum), then for several years (1993–1996) she worked as a lecturer at the Music Faculty of the Sumy Makarenko State Pedagogical University, teaching composition and piano, lecturing on music theory and history, and receiving the academic title of associate professor.

Ovcharenko has always shown a great interest in Ukrainian song folklore and founded several ensembles that collected, studied, and performed traditional Ukrainian music, preserving traditions and national artistic heritage. In particular, while teaching at the Mykola Lysenko Kyiv Secondary Specialized Music Boarding School, she created the *'Simonove Zelo' folklore ensemble*, providing talented creative youth with the opportunity to discover Ukrainian national culture, history, and art through music. In Sumy, the performances of the *Malva Ensemble*, founded by Ovcharenko and in which she was a performer, were broadcast on regional radio and television. With her folklore ensembles, Ovcharenko toured Ukraine and abroad, often spending the summer months traveling to Ukrainian villages and collecting folklore material – samples of traditional music, dances, rituals and customs. Halyna was also a long-time performer in the famous Kyiv ensemble of researchers and performers of Ukrainian folk music *Drevo* (artistic director – Yevhen Yefremov).

Ovcharenko's creative achievements in composition have been repeatedly recognized by prestigious Ukrainian prizes and awards. The year 1992 was a fruitful year for the young artist: she won the All-Ukrainian Competition of Choral Works (for three pieces for choir *Springing*, 1989), the International Competition of Marian and Ivanna Kots (for the cantata for choir, symphony orchestra, soloists and reader *Burnt Mallow* based on the poem by Valentyna Otroschenko, 1992), and the State Prize named after Mykola Leontovych.¹³ Ovcharenko's work *Predkovichne* (*Everlasting*) for chamber orchestra and ensemble of authentic voices (1995) won the International Competition for Women Composers in Kyiv in 1995.

¹³ Shurova, Nina: „Ovcharenko, Halyna Ivanivna“, *Encyklopediia Suchasnoii Ukrainy*. https://esu.com.ua/search_articles.php?id=74792

Blossoming talent and European recognition

In the mid-1990s, Halyna Ovcharenko began to actively enter the European cultural space and was recognized for her compositional talent by the international music community. The list of her international awards is impressive. In 1996, she received a grant from the University of Bristol (UK) and ORS to pursue a PhD in music composition at the University of Bristol, which she successfully completed in 2002. During her studies, she was twice awarded the Raymond Warren Prize in Music Composition at the University of Bristol (in 1998 and 1999). In 1996–1998, she also perfected her compositional skills in the Netherlands and Poland, in particular, she took part in a course for young composers under the guidance of the prominent Polish composer Krzysztof Penderecki. In 1998, she was awarded a scholarship from the University of Amsterdam to attend the summer courses in ethnomusicology ‘Hidden Messages: Culture and Communication’. She has also received prizes, awards and grants from international foundations such as PRS (2003), The Bliss Trust (2004), Arts Council of England (2004), etc. In 2005, she was awarded a grant from the International Society for Contemporary Music to work at the Visby International Composers' Center in Sweden.

After moving to the United Kingdom in 1996, Ovcharenko continues her active compositional work, expanding her arsenal of musical genres and attracting an ever-wider audience. The genre spectrum of the ‘British’ period of Ovcharenko's compositional work is quite extensive. Her compositions include pieces for solo instruments (including piano), ensembles, chamber, symphony, and brass orchestras, choir, chamber cantatas, vocal and instrumental works for voice and piano, music for theater and documentary films. It was in the UK that Ovcharenko first turned to the field of musical theater, writing the opera *Sketch* (1996, libretto by V. Vitkevych).

One of Ovcharenko's most popular works is the composition *Invocation of Rain* for four percussionists and an authentic voice (1996), which was performed at international music festivals in Ukraine, Britain, Romania, Croatia, and Slovenia. The composer's oeuvre was enriched by such works as the *String Quartet* (1996), the piece for symphony orchestra *Transformations* (1997), three compositions for choir ‘*Moods*’ based on the poems of William Butler Yeats (1997), a lyrical story for 18 strings *Illusion* (1997, commissioned by the English Chamber Orchestra), the piece *Le Nonsense* for harp and authentic voice based on texts from the poetry of Edward Lear (1997), *A Study of Witchcraft* for symphony orchestra (1999), music for the documentary film *On the Threshold* (1997, directed by A. Shylov).

The 2000s were marked in H. Ovcharenko's work by the composition and successful performance of two ballets – *The Last Battle* based on the text by Clive Staples Lewis (2000, commissioned by the London Children's Ballet, staged at the Peacock Theatre, West End London, May 2000) and *Kupala Night* based on the text by Mykola Gogol (2001, staged by the National Opera and Ballet Theater

of Ljubljana, Slovenia in 2003). Ovcharenko's ballets have been highly praised by professional critics in the British and international press and have brought the composer awards and well-deserved recognition. In particular, the British press wrote about the ballet *The Last Battles*: "Composer Halyna Ovcharenko has created a ballet full of beauty and delight that brings to life the last book of C. S. Lewis's epic *The Chronicles of Narnia*"¹⁴ [official website of Halyna Ovcharenko]. A correspondent of the popular British newspaper *The Independent on Sunday* vividly described his impressions of the production:

[...] Galina Ovcharenko's colorful, well-crafted score for small orchestra gives the performance a fierce professional gloss – from expressive folk melodies to terrifying brass climaxes worthy of Prokofiev. There were moments when, against the backdrop of a realistic burning fire, a smoke-filled battle scene, army formations, and yet another orchestral pile-up, I had to convince myself that this was a children's play [...].¹⁵

Ovcharenko's second ballet, *Kupala Night*, was also a great success, winning the prestigious International Competition The Three World Ballets ISCM in 2002, and then performed by the National Opera and Ballet Theater of Ljubljana at the World Music Days Festival in Slovenia in 2003.

In addition to ballets, the composer's oeuvre has been enriched by numerous orchestral, chamber, and choral works, including, in particular, *A Shimmering Silence* for string orchestra (2000), *Ebony Clarinet Quartet* (2002, commissioned by the Ebony Quartet from Belgium), pieces for the Bristol Youth Orchestra (2004), *Bring Forth the Horse* for a cappella male choir based on Lord Byron's *Mazepa* (2004, commissioned by the Bulava Men's Choir, London), *Melting Light* for cello and piano (2005), *What the Shaman Saw* for five percussionists (2005), *Polyphonic Pastorals* for 24 flutes (2006, commissioned by the French Flute Orchestra), *There Was a Shimmering Silence* for string orchestra (2007), *"Thy Kingdom Come, Thy Will Be Done..."* for symphony orchestra (2007), a piece for wind band *Fun for a Wind Ensemble* (2012), works for clarinet ensemble (2011–2015), etc.

Ovcharenko is a recognized master of instrumental arrangement, with numerous arrangements of traditional songs of the world (including Christmas songs) in various styles for piano and orchestra, piano and various ensembles, piano duet, and clarinet orchestra. In particular, a series of compositions commissioned by the clarinet ensemble *March of Dwarfs*, *Lezginka*, *Chicky-Vicky*, *Ukrainian Joke*, *Romani-Romani*, *Towards the Light*, *Tango*, etc. became very popular, entered the repertoire of several European clarinet orchestras and was performed in Holland, Norway, Belgium, England, Germany and other countries.

¹⁴ Composer Halyna Ovcharenko's personal website <http://www.halynaovcharenko.com/index.php#>

¹⁵ Signs of perfection in minimal movement. *The Independent on Sunday*, May 21, 2000. <http://www.halynaovcharenko.com/index.php>

Ovcharenko is invited to cooperate with leading European publishers of music literature. 2009–2010, Ovcharenko worked on the commission of Oxford University Press on the arrangement of famous classical works for piano duets. In 2011, Spartan Press published original piano duets by Ovcharenko together with her arrangements of classical music for piano duets.

In recent years, the composer has been fruitfully collaborating with leading creative teams and performers in Europe. Ovcharenko's music has been commissioned by the English Chamber Orchestra, the BBC London Symphony Orchestra, the Scottish National Ensemble, the London Children's Ballet, the Society for the Promotion of New Music, the Ebony Quartet of clarinetists from Belgium, the Orchestre des flautistes from France, and many other solo and ensemble performers. Such works by Ovcharenko as *There was a Shimmering Silence* for string orchestra, *Polyphonic Pastorals* for flute orchestra and *Thy Kingdom Come, Thy Will Be Done...* for symphony orchestra were performed by leading symphony orchestras: Scottish Ensemble, Ukrainian National Chamber Orchestra, BBC London Symphony Orchestra, etc.

Having lived in the UK for about 30 years, Ovcharenko continues her successful compositional and academic career, teaching piano, music theory and composition at Bristol Grammar School BGS and Taunton King's Hall. At the invitation of educational institutions and artistic societies, she gives lectures on folklore studies and contemporary Ukrainian music. She teaches composition virtually for students from different countries and at the international courses 'Encore Music Projects' UK. She is passionate about nurturing young talent and has donated her own funds to award prizes to the winners in the Young Composers category at the Bristol and Weston-super-Mare music festivals.

The composer has her own website, which reveals her multifaceted creative activity.¹⁶ For her successful work and professional achievements, Ovcharenko has a personal entry in *The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians*, second edition.¹⁷

Features of Halyna Ovcharenko's Compositional Style (the case of *Invocation of Rain*)

The main tendency of Halyna Ovcharenko's work is determined by her reliance on Ukrainian peasant folklore, and folk music is the basis of all her works. In her attempts to give folk songs a symphonic sound, the composer faced the problem of combining folk sources and complex modern compositional techniques. In the early 'Ukrainian' period of her work, she was particularly attracted to choral cycles, among the most famous of which are the *Chumak Songs* based on seasonal texts and games, and the *Burnt Mallow* deals with the Chernobyl

¹⁶ Composer Halyna Ovcharenko's personal website <http://www.halynaovcharenko.com/index.php#>

¹⁷ Shurova, Nina: „Ovcharenko, Halyna”, *The New Grove Dictionary of Music and Musicians*, New York, 2001, vol. 18, p. 817.

tragedy. In *Predkovichne (Everlasting)* she shows a deep sympathy for the pagan roots of Ukrainian culture and her attitude to the position of humanity in the universe.

It is important that even after moving to the UK and being 'included' in the cultural and artistic life of this country, Ovcharenko did not lose touch with her ethnic homeland and continues to identify herself as a representative of Ukrainian culture. Already in exile, she composed works with a strong national color, including the already mentioned ballet *Kupala Night* based on Mykola Gogol (2001), *Bring the Horse* for a cappella male choir (2004), *Thy Kingdom Come, Thy Will Be Done...* (2007), and other works genetically linked to Ukrainian musical folklore and spiritual traditions of Orthodoxy.

One of her most frequently performed works, *Invocation of Rain* for four percussionists and an authentic voice (1996), gives an idea of Ovcharenko's compositional style. It was recognized by the British Society for the Promotion of New Music as one of the best contemporary compositions of 2004 and performed in five European countries, including the Bucharest Festival in Romania in 2004 and the ISCM World Music Days in Zagreb, Croatia in 2005.

The work symbolically recreates a ritual that existed in pagan times not only in Ukraine but also in the cultures of many nations (for example, in Romania, North Macedonia, Belarus, and the countries of the Caucasus region), performed during a period of drought to summon rain and accompanied by ritual songs and dances. Ovcharenko discovered the ancient ritual of invoking rain during one of her folklore expeditions to the north of Sumy region. As stated in the author's notes to the score,

in old times, in a dry summer, villagers would drown a chaste widow in the river as a sacrifice to God, hoping for rain. This ceremony came from pagan (pre-Christian) times but during the last few centuries has omitted the actual sacrifice and lived on as a game. Nevertheless old people who still retain this tradition sincerely believe in the magical power of their action.¹⁸

The composer was so impressed by this ancient ritual of sacrifice that she decided to create her own musical interpretation of it. Her concept carries the binary of the eternal philosophical opposition of life and death: on the one hand, it is the personal drama of a widow who sacrifices herself for the common good, and on the other hand, the joy of a community hoping for the rain that will bring life. The author's preface also states that the opening song is an invocation from an authentic ritual. The other materials (music and poetry) belong to the composer herself.

The text used in the work requires special attention. Structurally, it is divided into six fragments, which are related to different parts of the ancient ritual: *Widow's Monologue*, *Traditional Song*, *Prayer and Invocation*, *Widow's Song*, *Lament*, and *Epilogue*.

¹⁸ Ovcharenko, Halyna: *Invocation of Rain* for authentic voice and drums, Manuscript of the score, 24 pp.

The initial *Widow's Monologue* is a kind of semantic 'opening', which states the unfavorable weather conditions of the summer season, which could have resulted in a deterioration in people's well-being – a long absence of rain and incredible heat: "Not a single drop of rain so far; The pitiless sun is cracking the earth, exhausting it. Unbearable heat. The unendurable sun". The closing words of the *Monologue* "It is time for offering the Great Sacrifice" are a declaration of the moment of sacrifice. As indicated in the author's commentary, the text of the *Widow's Monologue* should be read slowly, deliberately stretching the hissing sounds of sh, s, ch, t, z.

The next two episodes, *Traditional Song* and *Prayer and Invocation*, use authentic folk texts. The *Traditional Song* is the first musical and poetic fragment of the work, which preserves the phonetic style of the northern border region of Sumy ("doshchichek", "polyvaychichek") and the traditional Ukrainian song folklore of gukas at the end of phrases: "I have knocked I have clamoured but no rain, no rain. Gu! Rain water, water".

Prayer and Invocation is the next spoken episode, which reflects the belief of the ancient Slavs in the effectiveness of appeasing the forces of nature. The text of the invocation is spoken, according to the author's instructions, excitedly with a gradual acceleration of the tempo and an increase in the sound of the voice: "Come on Rain, come on. I will make borsch soup in an earthen Pot for you, will put one in a corner. The earthen pot will crack, the sky will shine with a flash of lightning. Come on Rain, come on to the kale fields, to the dry grass, to the small flowers, to the little children!"

Both the texts and the musical embodiment of the next two fragments – *Widow's Song* and *Lament* – are the author's own, written in the folklore style. Ovcharenko has shown a remarkable poetic talent and transformed her vast experience of recording and researching examples of oral folk songwriting into her work. The lyrics of the song tell of three birds flying to God himself to ask for rain. The stylistics of the text is enriched by figurative and poetic metaphors of birds that can "break open the sky with their beaks to let out the water". The verbs at the end of each phrase that are broken off during repetition are also related to the style of the Ukrainian folk song and poetry tradition.

The last, most tragic section of the work, *Lament*, is written in the textual style of Polissya laments and social songs. A mother seems to be addressing her two young sons, telling them about the hard life of a family that has lost their father: "Oh, Children-flowers, you are little boys. What a hard lot you have. Your father went off. He is lying in the tomb. He cannot see his darlings." In the final part of the lament, the widow informs her sons that they will soon be completely orphaned, as she must sacrifice herself for the common good of society: "Children-flowers, what a hard lot you have. Your mother will go off too. She will take wing to God. She will ask for happiness for everybody."

The *Epilogue* of the work is semantically and intonationally related to the previous part, *Lament*, but has a more enlightened, soothingly lyrical character: "Oh,

Children-flowers. Your mother will come back. She will turn into a cuckoo. She will cry, she will tell you stories. She will cheer you up.”

The musical embodiment of the ancient sacred ritual in Halyna Ovcharenko's composition is based on singing in the Ukrainian folk tradition and a wide range of performing tools on modern percussion instruments with a certain and indefinite pitch¹⁹. The idea of combining Ukrainian authentic singing and percussion was first realized in a 1992 Ukrainian-French music project involving members of the Ukrainian folk group *Drevo* and the French percussion group *Baron Samedi Perkussions*. The collaboration resulted in the release of two CDs (1992 and 1998). Obviously, the original modern arrangement of folklore, the wide international resonance of the first part of the Ukrainian-French project, and Ovcharenko's long (about 10 years) participation in the *Drevo* ensemble influenced the formation of the stylistic guidelines of her own composition.

The score of *Invocation of Rain* contains about 30 names of percussion instruments, including both traditional ones (for example, timpani, xylophone, vibraphone, various drums, temple blocks, cymbals, maracas, cow bells, etc.) and non-traditional ones. The latter include, in particular, the *doli*, rattle, and *gala-gala*. The *doli* is an ancient oriental drum popular in the Caucasus. The body is made of a tree trunk, 25–30 cm high and 35–40 cm in diameter. It is played with hands, fingers, and sticks. The instrument is covered with leather on the top and bottom, so it can be played from both sides. The main type of rattle (English Rattle, Italian Raganella, French Crecelle) looks like a small wooden wheel with ‘teeth’ and a handle attached to it. When the wheel rotates, it touches a wooden or plastic plate with its teeth, which makes a dry crackling sound. *Gala-gala* is a wooden/plastic/metal plate, about the size of a school ruler, with a 30–40 centimeter long string attached to it. When the percussionist spins it overhead, from the side or front (where safe), it makes a buzzing sound.

The percussion in *Invocation of Rain* is used in aleatoric and sonorous episodes of imitation of the forces of nature that frame the work. The gradation of sounds is extremely wide, and this helps to recreate the picture of a sacred sacrifice, in which every sound has a symbolic meaning, such as the friction of some objects with greater or lesser intensity, blows on a wooden box, the clatter of stones, rustling, the sound of flexaton, bells, imitation of distant thunder, etc. Another function of the percussion in this piece is a ritual accompaniment to singing. Sometimes the elastic, incendiary rhythms of timpani, cymbals, large and small drums, xylophone, and bells recreate the powerful energy of a ritual dance.

The female voice is also used in the work in two hypostases: spoken episodes (utterance of individual phrases) alternate with authentic singing. The composer demands remarkable acting skills from the singer, who must demonstrate a wide range of verbal and musical possibilities of the voice, from the barely audible

¹⁹ Ovcharenko, Halyna: *Invocation of Rain* for authentic voice and drums. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xOwNVRPChxc>

whisper of a person exhausted from the heat (Sheet Music Example 1) to the utterance of incantations and authentic singing, the most effective part of the sacrifice rite.

Sheet music example 1

Imitating wind Ad libitum

Lento
Read the text purposely stretching hissing sounds. Underlined syllables must be stressed

7 30" Ше доСі Жодного доШу. БеЗЖалиСне Соние Шмагує, виСнадЖує Землю

- 2 -

Fragments of songs of the calendar and ritual cycle (in this case, harvest songs of the Sumy region) borrowed from Ukrainian song folklore reveal the verbal and musical richness of the national cultural tradition, in which worship of the forces of nature-sun, wind, and rain-occupies an important place. The first authentic episode is an incantation song from the ritual "I knocked, I knocked, but there was no rain. Gu!" (Sheet Music Examples 2, 3):

In the vocal phrases of the Lament and the Epilogue, one can hear the intonations of Ukrainian laments, as well as social songs, including lullabies, which contain images of mothers, children, and birds.

The work uses not only singing and spoken lines by the performer. At the end of the last part of *Lament*, the percussionists, along with the soloist, whisper when they hear thunder: "God's sign", and at the very end of the piece, they whisper "The time of the great sacrifice". This phrase is a kind of semantic archway to the beginning of the piece.

Sheet music example 2

Molto Rubato
♩ = 42

Piu mosso (♩ = 65) *Molto Rubato*
To sing with open voice
(traditional, authentic manner of singing)

Voice: По - сту-ка - ла поєро - ка - ла

Perc. I: Vibra arco, Xylo

Perc. II: Cymbal arco

Perc. III: Glock arco, Flessaton, Glock arco

Perc. IV: Chocalo

Sheet music example 3

Voice: а до - шу не-ма а до-шуде-ма Гу! А до-шечек по-п'

Perc. I: Vibra arco

Perc. II: Xylo

Perc. III: Glock arco

Perc. IV: * Crotalle F, Timps

* Put Crotalle F on top of the Timp. Hit it and vibrate the sound with the Timp pedal.

The second song (author's) fragment of the work features a more lively melody, "Oh, Three Birds Fly" (Sheet Music Example 4).

Conclusions

Halyna Ovcharenko belongs to the group of those figures of Ukrainian musical culture who successfully combine national artistic traditions with modern European achievements in composition in their diverse works. In her attempts to provide folk songs with instrumental arrangements, the composer successfully solves the problem of combining folklore sources and complex modern compositional techniques. In this respect, Ovcharenko's work can be attributed to the neofolklore trend of twenty-first century music. At the same time, her works demonstrate her mastery of the most modern compositional techniques and means of musical expression, as evidenced by the numerous honors, grants, and prizes she has received from cultural institutions in various European countries. In an effort to integrate into the European cultural environment as soon as possible and to unleash her creative potential, Ovcharenko has made considerable efforts to im-

Sheet music example 4

75 *Molto Rubato* *follow the pitch pattern* *ff* *falsetto* *ord.* *falsetto*

Voice *Ой лє-гит' три пташ-ки до са-мо-о го до са-мо-го Бо До са-мо-го Бо-о*

Perc. I

Perc. II *ff*

Perc. III *Toms*

Perc. IV *Timps* *mf*

78 *ord.* *falsetto* *ord.* *falsetto*

Voice *Кри-ла-ми ма-ха-ти Бо-жень-ку, Бо-жень-ку Бо-жень-ку про-ха-а*

Perc. I

Perc. II

Perc. III

Perc. IV

- 10 -

prove her professional skills and continue her musical education abroad. After obtaining a professional musical education and starting her career in Ukraine, she studied composition in the UK and received artistic grants in Poland, the Netherlands, and Sweden. At the same time, during her long stay abroad, Ovcharenko did not lose touch with her ethnic homeland, made and continues to make significant efforts to promote Ukrainian culture, create a positive image of Ukraine through culture and art, and acts as a true cultural ambassador of Ukraine in the world. Halyna Ovcharenko's creative, pedagogical, musical, and performing activities not only contribute to the expansion of Ukrainian-European cultural ties, but also serve a high goal of establishing the image of Ukraine as a European country with ancient historical and cultural traditions and modern achievements.